

ONGOING SITUATION OF POLICIES FOR SUPPORTING VULNERABLE GROUPS GAINING ACCESS TO ONLINE PUBLIC SERVICE IN THE DIGITAL ERA

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Abstract

In the ever more interconnected world thanks to the invention of the internet, it is important to make sure that everyone can secure their own rights to access the modern online public services, especially the vulnerable groups. This paper will analyze the current state and present challenges in rolling out these policies to support the vulnerable groups in District 12, Ho Chi Minh City; and from there making suggestions to improve the coverage of said policies.

Keywords: Vulnerable Groups, Online Public Service, Digitalization.

1. BASES OF ARGUMENTS ON VULNERABLE GROUPS ACCESSING ONLINE PUBLIC SERVICES

“Vulnerable groups” is a term coined and used widely in international documents and research about human rights, used to denote individuals or a community having weaker power in economy, social footing or politics, thus, being more vulnerable to rights violations. According to World Bank, the vulnerable groups are individuals who are highly susceptible to poverty due to demographic characteristics, geographic challenges, or special societal situations (World Bank, 2021). UNESCO then expands it to include the homeless, unemployed, persons with disabilities, and troubled youth (UNESCO, 2022)

In the ever-accelerating digitalization future, as stated by E-Government Development Index – EGDI (2022), the vulnerable groups in the online-focused environment includes individuals who has difficulty with, or even inability to, access online public services and information; and even if they have access to it, are burdened by the economic cost to maintain it. The people that may be affected are: individuals in poverty, elders, people with disabilities, people of minority, residents of remote areas, unregistered workers, immigrants and refugees.

In this paper, the author focuses on three groups of people representing the vulnerable groups in accessing online public services in Vietnam: the elderly, persons with disability and people with low-income

2. THE POLICIES IN SUPPORTING VULNERABLE GROUPS ACCESSING ONLINE PUBLIC SERVICES

Public policies are a collection of frameworks, solutions designed and issued by the government, aiming to solve problems encountered by the people in their daily life. According to Decree No. 34/2016/ND-CP, public policies include frameworks and solutions to solve

problems encountered by the people with clear goals and full transparency, for the good of the people

To advance towards proficient digital public services, making and rolling out policies to support the vulnerable groups accessing said services is an important section in the general development plan. However, due to the specific situations of these groups, the policies won't be a separate document but rather intertwined within various strategies, plans and frameworks.

These policies are meant to be interconnected by multiple branches and fields; as well as needing the collaboration of many different bodies: the government, sociopolitical organizations and even private sectors. The policy doesn't stop at only providing the technical infrastructure (such as devices, internet connection), but it also includes improving the people's technological affinity, their ability to access the internet and information; this may also bring adjustments to the administrative procedures to better suit the abilities of the vulnerable groups and to ensure personal data security

Thus, policies that support vulnerable groups accessing online public services not only demonstrate humanitarian efforts and societal equality, but also allow for progression of steady growth and advancement of administrative quality in the online era.

3. THE CURRENT STATE OF THESE POLICIES IN DISTRICT 12, HO CHI MINH CITY

3.1. Responsibilities distribution

The people's committee of District 12 had issued many plans and role assignments to all of their agencies to push along the policies of supporting the vulnerable groups accessing online public services. However, field survey suggests that up to 17.8% of staffs on duty report that their assignment isn't clear, and there's a problem with crossing, duplicate roles. All of these affect the effectiveness in rolling out the policies (Chart 3.1)

Chart 3.1: The quality in role assignment and objectives in executing the policy

Source: Survey

At the same time, the highlight of the operation is how the cooperation is kept in sync throughout. The leading departments like Project 06 Department, Smart Urban Department are formed with systemic structure to ensure the operation can run smoothly. The involvement of the police department, sociopolitical associates and community efforts have all empowered this movement greatly

3.2. The role of the police force and the youth union

District 12’s police force assigned as the main task force for Project 06 Department had formed and mobilize specialized teams for project details, public services, technical support and finance – HR. Remarkably, operating Online public service portal at congdoc.catphcm.bocongan.gov.vn had provided up to 162 administrative procedures, adding to the effort to digitalize public services.

In addition, the Youth Union had mobilized a team for communal technological support in accordance to directive issued by the city; the aim is to help the people to gain more technological proficiency, especially during the Youth Month of 2023 with activities for training regarding online public services and online payment.

3.3. Assessing the project’s sufficiency

The survey result illustrated by the chart 3.2 and 3.3 reflects the difference between staffs’ self-assessment and the people’s acknowledgment about the project’s sufficiency:

Chart 3.2: Rating the financial and equipment sufficiency during the project (as rated by the staff)

Source: Survey

- Finances: 32.2% of staffs said the financial resources are sufficient, while only 9.3% of the people agree
- Equipment: 31.1% of staffs gave high rating, but only 7.6% of the people share the same view

Chart 3.3: Rating the finance and equipment sufficiency during the project (as rated by the people)

Source: Survey

The difference shown here proves a more in-depth investigation is needed to look into the distribution of resources, and at the same time, improve communication efforts and transparency.

4. SUGGESTING SOLUTIONS TO IMPROVE PROFICIENCY OF POLICIES TO SUPPORT VULNERABLE GROUPS ACCESSING ONLINE PUBLIC SERVICES

Based on the analytics of the current state of the project and obstacles encountered, this paper suggests a few solutions:

4.1. Review and refine role assignments

Need to review all imposed rules about role assignments and missions between agencies and related partners to eliminate unwanted role crossing and duplicates. Regulations about cooperation between different fields need to be properly documented into text, clear directives and have full transparency on moderation as well as penalties for violations

4.2. Secure financial resources and equipments

The government needs to prioritize funding activities aiding the vulnerable groups, especially the technological infrastructure (terminal, public internet, free wifi, etc.). At the same time, diversify resources through collaborations between public and private agencies, encouraging tech companies to join forces.

4.3. Improve the vulnerable groups' technological affinity

Open classes to introduce and help the people learn and navigate online public services; the classes need to be appropriate to each demographic (the elderly; persons with disability; people in poverty, etc.). Can mobilize the youth volunteer to aid directly at the local area. These activities should also be integrated into national programs to push back poverty; as well as digital transformation.

4.4. Streamlining public services and improve the interface of online public services

Streamlining the administrative procedures to be simpler and user friendly, integrating and automating the process. The user interface should be more intuitive and easier to use; in addition, integrating sign language, text-to-speech, and visual guide/instruction video.

4.5. Strengthen regulations regarding moderation, feedback and rating

Establishing a feedback channel for the vulnerable group during the usage of online public service, collecting said feedback then improve the policies. At the same time, have a system of periodic rating about the policy's coverage and effectiveness, centralize on the user.

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